

Biosensor transport assay for SLC1A2 using HEK293-SLC1A2- WTOE cells

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Assay description

This assay detects aspartate uptake using a biosensor for aspartate, cyto-iAspSnFR (Addgene #201394) in HEK293-JumpIn-TRex cells overexpressing SLC1A2. Aspartate uptake leads in an increased emission in the GFP channel that is normalized to the red fluorescent protein mScarlet-I for expression level normalization. Fluorescence detection is performed using a flow cytometer for increased throughput and high cell number statistics.

Assay protocol

2 Mio cells (HEK293-JumpIn-TRex-SLC1A2-WTOE-p1) were seeded in 10mL full medium (refers to 10% FCS (Gibco #10500064)/DMEM high-glucose, pyruvate, glutamax, phenolred Gibco #31966021), supplemented with 1 µg/mL doxycycline to induce SLC1A2 expression. The following day, the cells were transfected with cyto-iAspSnFR using Lipofectamine 3000 (ThermoFisher) according to the manufacturer's instructions, using the following amounts: 20 µg DNA, 40 µL P3000, 30 µL R3000, 500+500 µL OptiMEM). The following day, cells were starved for ~5-6 hours in 10% dialyzed FCS/DMEM (-glucose - pyruvate -glutamax), before harvesting cells. Cells were harvested by brief trypsinization, then taking cells in suspension in 10 mL of starvation medium. Cells were centrifugated, and taken up in 10% dia. FCS/PBS. For the assay, 100 µL cells suspension was combined with 100 µL PBS containing amino acids and test compounds. Cells were incubated for 30 min at r.t. (22 °C) before measurement was initialized at a BD Fortessa X-20 flow cytometer equipped with an HTS module. Optical configuration: sfGFP/FITC Ex 488 nm Em 530/30nm, mScarlet-I/PE-Texas Red Ex 561 nm, Em 610/20 nm. 80-100 µL were injected per sample and all events were recorded and stored for subsequent analysis in FlowJo 10. .Ffluoratio was derived by dividing FITC-A/PE-Texas Red-A.

Additional information

A non-sigmoid component for L-asp uptake is detected at very high external concentrations (>10 mM L-asp) that cannot be blocked by the inhibitor TFB-TBOA, indicating additional uptake not mediated by SLC1A2).

Target data

SLC	SLC1A2
Synonyms	EAAT2, EIEE41, GLT-1, HBGT
SLC sub-family	SLC1
UniProt ID	P43004
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE029E-6 HEK293-JumpIn-TRex-SLC1A2-WTOE-p1

Assay data

Dose response curve(s)	Compound name (1)	L-aspartic acid
	PubChem CID	5960
	Vendor (catalogue #)	

<p style="text-align: center;">HEK-SLC1A2 assay</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> — L-asp +0.04% DMSO — L-asp +0.04% DMSO — L-asp +10uM TFB-TBOA — L-asp +10uM TFB-TBOA </p>	<p>Mode of action</p> <p>EC50, IC50 (95% CI)</p>	<p>Substrate</p> <p>Curve 1: L-aspartic acid: 11 μM (9-13 μM) Curve 2: L-aspartic acid: 18 μM (15-22 μM)</p>
	<p>Compound name (2)</p> <p>PubChem CID</p> <p>Vendor (catalogue #)</p> <p>Mode of action</p> <p>EC50, IC50 (95% CI)</p>	<p>TFB TBOA</p> <p>52941382</p> <p></p> <p>Inhibitor</p> <p></p>

Discussion

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).
- <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.05.04.537313>